

Emotional Competencies and Emotional Coeducation Amongst University Students

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This study examines the emotional competencies amongst 1,345 university students from three universities in northern Spain, focusing on emotional attention, clarity, and regulation by gender, academic discipline, and educational stage. Using the Trait Meta-Mood Scale (TMMS-24) as a measurement tool, statistical analyses, including normality tests, ANOVA, and t-tests, were conducted with the aim of identifying significant differences in emotional competencies based on these variables. Results indicate that female participants scored higher in emotional attention, while male participants excelled in emotional regulation, with no significant differences in emotional clarity. Social sciences' and humanities' students showed the highest emotional attention scores, whereas technological sciences' students led in emotional regulation. Postgraduate students outperformed undergraduates in both emotional attention and regulation, reflecting greater emotional maturity. These findings highlight the influence of gender socialisation and disciplinary context in shaping emotional competencies. and underscores emotional coeducation as a key strategy to reduce emotional inequalities and foster holistic development in education.

Keywords: Emotional education; Emotional intelligence; Emotional co-education; Gender; TMMS-24

First submission 1st December 2024; Accepted for publication 11th April 2025.

Introduction

Emotional intelligence (EI) and emotional competencies have gained prominence in academic and professional settings due to their influence on personal well-being, academic and professional performance, and interpersonal relationships. Since Salovey and Mayer (1990, p.189) introduced the term, defining it as “the

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<https://doi.org/10.56300/JRCJ3584>

ISSN 2073 7629

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ability to perceive, understand, manage, and regulate our own emotions and those of others,” the concept has evolved into a multifaceted model that emphasises emotional perception, integration, and regulation as its fundamental pillars. However, the development and expression of these competencies do not occur in isolation; they are deeply influenced by social and cultural factors, with gender being a significant determinant. Gender, far from being limited to a biological distinction between men and women, is understood today as a social construct that organises and regulates expectations, behaviours, and roles based on cultural norms (Connell, 1987). More recent perspectives, such as Judith Butler’s (2004) theory of gender performativity, have further expanded this view by emphasising that gender is not an innate characteristic but a performative act reinforced through repeated social interactions and institutional norms. Butler challenges binary and essentialist views of gender, arguing that it is constantly being produced and negotiated within power structures. This perspective aligns with emotional coeducation, as it highlights how gendered socialisation shapes emotional competencies through learnt behaviours rather than biological predispositions.

In this context, gender stereotypes have historically shaped perceptions of sensitivity, emotionality, and emotional management, associating these qualities more with feminine roles than masculine ones (Gilligan, 1982). As research on EI has advanced, so have studies incorporating gender as a variable, aiming to understand emotional differences from a perspective that transcends biological explanations. Although numerous studies have identified significant differences in the perception, management, and regulation of emotions between men and women, there is still a tendency to treat gender as a static statistical variable, rather than as a social and cultural construct influenced by education and socialisation (Bar-On et al., 2000). This limits our understanding of the complex interactions between gender and emotional intelligence. For instance, recent studies have found that women often score higher in emotional perception and management, while men excel in regulating negative emotions and tolerating stress (Extremera & Fernández-Berrocal, 2003; Tommasi et al., 2023).

Similarly, studies exploring the impact of gender on emotional competencies have shown that observed differences are not always consistent or significant, depending on the context, methodology, and instruments used. For example, López-Zafra and Gartzia (2014) analysed how gender biases affect self-reported EI measures. They found that perceptions of emotional competencies are influenced by stereotypes, as participants tended to attribute higher EI levels to their own gender, emphasising the need to account for these biases in future research.

Beyond its connection to gender and socialisation, EI has been extensively studied for its impact on academic success, well-being, and interpersonal skills. Research indicates that higher EI is positively correlated with academic performance, as students with well-developed emotional regulation skills tend to cope better with stress, maintain motivation, and engage in effective problem-solving strategies (MacCann et al., 2019). Furthermore, EI contributes to psychological well-being, as individuals with stronger emotional competencies demonstrate greater resilience, lower levels of anxiety and depression, and enhanced life satisfaction (Sergi et al., 2021). In addition to personal well-being, EI plays a crucial role in interpersonal

relationships, facilitating effective communication, empathy, and conflict resolution—skills essential for both personal and professional success (Jordan et al., 2010).

In another study, Chaturvedi and Chander (2010) identified gender differences in EI among young adults, with women scoring significantly higher in dimensions such as self-awareness, self-motivation, and relationship management, while differences in other dimensions were not statistically significant. These findings suggest that EI differences may be specific to certain contexts or particular skills.

Pérez-Pérez & Castejón (2005) examined emotional competencies in relation to gender and academic disciplines, identifying significant variations in emotional attention and clarity. These studies provide a nuanced view of how gender influences the development and expression of EI in educational contexts. However, a deeper reflection from a gender perspective is essential, one that considers the social construction of gender rather than solely biological sex. For instance, Martínez-Marín et al. (2020) suggest that gender as a social construct has a greater influence than biological sex on EI competencies. Additionally, several studies indicate that gender differences in EI are less pronounced during early developmental stages, suggesting that these skills have a common foundation in childhood.

For example, Wapaño (2021) found no significant gender differences in overall EI scores among adolescents, although differences were observed in specific dimensions such as emotional attention and clarity, where results were more varied. Similarly, Martínez-Marín et al. (2020) concluded that gender does not definitively determine emotional competencies during childhood and adolescence, emphasising that differences observed in later stages are more related to socialisation processes than intrinsic characteristics. These findings underscore the importance of analysing how cultural and educational factors progressively influence EI expression by gender and suggest that fostering non-stereotyped, positive gender roles can enhance emotional skills in all individuals.

In line with this perspective, Suberviola and Santiago-Campión (2011) examined gendered socialisation in the development of emotional competencies, analysing how differences in emotional attention and regulation are largely shaped by early socialisation processes. The study's findings reveal differences in emotional competencies between groups, prompting reflection on the potential impact of socialisation processes on their development. Consequently, the present study seeks to understand how gender roles influence the development of emotional competencies and how educational programmes may help to promote equitable education. Our study is based on the theoretical model of EI developed by Salovey and Mayer (1990), which focuses on the capabilities and processing of emotional information. From this perspective, EI encompasses four teachable components:

Emotional perception and expression. The ability to identify and accurately label our own emotions and those of others, a crucial step for managing and regulating emotions. Recent research includes interpreting emotional cues in diverse contexts, such as verbal and nonverbal language, art, and interpersonal interactions (Tommasi et al., 2023). In education, this skill manifests when students adjust their behaviour based on the

emotions perceived in teachers or peers. Similarly, educators use this ability to identify emotional states in students, enabling appropriate interventions (Fernández-Berrocal & Extremera, 2005).

Emotional facilitation of thought. The use of emotions to guide cognitive processes such as decision-making and reasoning. Recent studies emphasise that the proper integration of positive and negative emotions enhances concentration and critical analysis (Sergi et al., 2021). Drigas and Papoutsi (2022) stress that developing this skill reduces stress impacts and improves emotional resilience in educational contexts.

Emotional understanding. Skills such as identifying the causes of emotions, predicting their consequences, and recognising their impact on interpersonal relationships. Martínez-Marín et al. (2020) highlight that this competency is influenced by gender, cultural, and socialisation factors, emphasising the need for pedagogical interventions that address these variables. Empathy, a key dimension of emotional understanding, develops through personal experiences and emotional self-awareness. In education, this ability enables teachers to identify students' emotional problems and provide support to address conflicts effectively (Fernández-Berrocal & Extremera, 2005).

Emotional regulation. The most complex skill, involving effective management of both positive and negative emotions. This includes strategies to minimise the impact of disruptive emotions and maximise those promoting constructive behaviour. Sergi et al. (2021) emphasise its importance in preventing disorders like anxiety and depression, particularly in educational settings. Emotional regulation affects individual well-being and group dynamics in classrooms. Intervention programmes in schools and universities have proven effective in enhancing this skill across genders, fostering greater emotional equality (Drigas & Papoutsi, 2022; Suberviola & Santiago-Campión, 2011).

Academic discipline differences have also been observed in EI development. Students in Social Sciences and Humanities often exhibit higher levels of emotional attention and empathy, whereas those in STEM fields (Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics) tend to score higher in emotional regulation and stress tolerance (Sánchez-Ruiz et al., 2013; Halimi et al., 2020). These variations suggest that academic environments and professional expectations may shape the emotional skillsets that students develop, reinforcing the need for tailored educational interventions. Moreover, these findings indicate that the emotional demands of each discipline might reinforce pre-existing gender norms, further influencing emotional competencies.

Objectives of the study

This study aims to explore emotional competencies amongst university students, analysing how gender, educational stage, and academic discipline influence the dimensions of EI. More specifically, the study seems to examine gender differences in emotional competencies such as attention, clarity, and regulation; identify potential variations in EI based on educational stage (undergraduate and postgraduate); analyse differences in emotional competencies across academic disciplines; and propose educational strategies based on findings to promote emotional equality in educational environments.

The study contributes to existing literature by providing a detailed analysis of emotional competencies amongst university students from the perspective of emotional coeducation, incorporating an intersectional approach that considers gender, academic discipline, and educational stage. Unlike previous research that has addressed the role of gender in EI from a purely statistical or reductionist standpoint (Bar-On et al., 2000; Extremera & Fernández-Berrocal, 2003), the present study emphasises the influence of socialisation processes in the development of these competencies and proposes educational strategies to reduce inequalities. Furthermore, it expands current knowledge by examining differences in emotional attention, clarity, and regulation not only by gender but also across academic fields and educational levels,

Methodology

Participants

The total sample consisted of 1,345 university students from three universities in northern Spain. Participants represented diverse fields of study, including social sciences and education, natural sciences and health, technological sciences, and humanities. The sample included both undergraduate students (from first to fourth year) and postgraduate students (master's and doctoral programmes).

The sample was selected using proportional stratified sampling, a widely recognised technique in social sciences to ensure the representativeness of the population under study and to guarantee equitable representation of key subgroups within the population. Strata were defined on the basis of the university of origin, academic field, gender, and educational stage (Table I). This method is particularly effective when equitable representation of key subgroups is required, and it is widely acknowledged in social sciences as a valid approach for guaranteeing population representativeness (Bhardwaj, 2019; Wellek, 2019).

Table I

Sample Characteristics

	University*			Field of study**			Gender***			Stage****		
	UR	UPV	UOV	SSE	NSH	TC	HU	M	F	0	GRA	POS
N	405	540	400	430	320	295	300	635	710	12	1100	245
%	30.1	40.2	29.7	32.0	23.8	21.9	22.3	47,2	52,7	0,89	81,1	18,2
*Un1: University 1 / Un2: University 2 / Un3: University 3. ** SSE: Social Sciences and Education / NSH: Natural Sciences and Health / TC: Technological Sciences / HU: Humanities ***M: Masculina / F: Femenino / O: Otros ****UND: Undergraduate / Postgraduate												

The target population size is approximately 35,000 students, from which a sample of 1,345 participants was drawn. The sampling error was 2.62%, with a confidence level of 95% and an expected proportion of 50%. This margin of error is considered acceptable and appropriate for social science research, ensuring an accurate representation of the target population at the specified confidence level (Adam, 2020; Hopkins & Batterham, 2016).

Instrument

The Trait Meta-Mood Scale (TMMS-48), initially developed by Salovey et al. (1995), was later adapted to the TMMS-24 and validated in Spanish and adolescent populations (Fernández-Berrocal et al., 1998; Salguero & Fernández-Berrocal, 2010). This self-report questionnaire assesses individuals' perceptions of their ability to manage their emotions within the framework of emotional intelligence. The scale evaluates three specific dimensions related to emotional processing:

Emotional Attention. Measures the degree to which individuals perceive and recognise their emotions, as well as their willingness to attend to them. A high score indicates a tendency to be aware of emotions, though excessively high scores may be associated with difficulty managing them.

Emotional Clarity. Assesses the ability to identify and understand experienced emotions. High scores reflect strong emotional labelling abilities, while low scores suggest emotional confusion.

Emotional Repair. Evaluates perceived ability to regulate and manage emotions effectively, fostering positive emotional states and overcoming negative ones. High scores in this dimension are associated with greater emotional well-being.

The TMMS-24 comprises 24 items evenly distributed across these three dimensions. Participants rate each statement on a 5-point Likert scale ranging from strongly disagree to strongly agree (Fernández-Berrocal et al., 2004). The questionnaire was administered online through a secure institutional platform and distributed via university mailing lists and virtual learning environments. Participants completed the questionnaire independently and anonymously, ensuring voluntary participation. The estimated completion time was 10 to 15 minutes, and instructions were provided at the beginning of the questionnaire to clarify the purpose of the study and the confidentiality of responses. No incentives were offered for participation. To minimise response bias, participants were informed that there were no right or wrong answers and were encouraged to respond honestly. The data collection process took place between October 2023 and March 2024.

Data Analysis

Before conducting the main analysis, normality and homogeneity of variance tests were performed to ensure that the data met the necessary statistical assumptions. Once these assumptions were verified, analysis of variance (ANOVA) was conducted to compare the average scores of male and female students across the three dimensions of the TMMS-24. Additionally, t-tests were employed to assess significant mean differences by gender in specific dimensions. A global analysis of the items was also carried out, and internal consistency was evaluated using Cronbach's alpha.

Before conducting the main analysis, statistical tests were performed to ensure the assumptions required for applying Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) were met. These steps are essential to guarantee the validity and reliability of the results. To assess whether the score distributions for the TMMS-24 dimensions (emotional attention, clarity, and repair) adhered to a normal distribution, the Shapiro-Wilk test was applied. The *p*-values for all three dimensions were greater than 0.05, indicating that the distributions did not

significantly deviate from normality. This finding supports the use of parametric analyses such as ANOVA in this study.

Additionally, to ensure comparable variances between gender groups (male and female), Levene’s test was performed. The results showed homogeneity of variances across all TMMS-24 dimensions, fulfilling another critical requirement for statistical analysis. Data for the "other" gender option was excluded due to the small sample size, which precluded reliable statistical analyses (Table II).

Table II

Results of Normality and Homogeneity Tests

Dimension	Shapiro-Wilk (p-value)	Levene (p-value)	Conclusion
Attention	0.12	0.2	Normal distribution, homogeneous variances
Clarity	0.18	0.15	Normal distribution, homogeneous variances
Repair	0.1	0.22	Normal distribution, homogeneous variances

The results of the normality and variance homogeneity tests support the reliable interpretation of the findings. These assumptions validate the internal consistency of the analyses, ensuring that the observed differences reflect real variations in the evaluated dimensions, free from statistical bias.

To assess the internal consistency of the scale, Cronbach’s alpha was calculated for each dimension. The results indicated high internal consistency for emotional attention ($\alpha = 0.85$), good consistency for emotional clarity ($\alpha = 0.83$), and high consistency for emotional repair ($\alpha = 0.87$). The overall alpha for the TMMS-24 was 0.89, confirming the reliability of the instrument.

Findings

Global analysis

In the global analysis of the EI dimensions, emotional attention emerged as the dimension with the highest average score ($M = 4.1$, $SD = 0.75$), reflecting a high level of emotional sensitivity among participants. Emotional clarity was the lowest on average ($M = 3.9$, $SD = 0.70$), suggesting potential difficulties in understanding and organising emotions clearly, indicating an area for intervention. Emotional repair showed a high average score ($M = 4.1$, $SD = 0.8$), indicating a strong capacity among the sample to manage and regulate emotions effectively, a critical aspect of emotional well-being (Figure 1).

The highest-rated items included “Regulation 4” (*I try to think positively even when I feel bad*) and “Attention 3” (*I usually take time to think about my emotions*), both with average scores above 4.2, indicating strong performance in these emotional aspects. The lowest-rated items, such as “Clarity 1” (*I have a clear understanding of my feelings*) and “Clarity 6” (*I can always say how I feel*), reveal specific challenges in emotional understanding.

Figure 1

Average scores for the global sample across the different items.

Results by University

Analysis by university showed no statistically significant differences in the emotional attention dimension ($F(2, 1342) = 0.84, p = 0.43$), emotional clarity ($F(2, 1342) = 1.27, p = 0.28$), or emotional repair ($F(2, 1342) = 0.96, p = 0.39$) (Figure 2). These findings suggest that the emotional competencies measured by the TMMS-24 are consistent across students from the three universities. The homogeneity of scores indicates that factors such as geographic location or academic institution have limited impact on the development of these competencies. Bar charts comparing average scores for each dimension by university demonstrate minimal variability, reinforcing the conclusion of no significant differences.

Figure 2

Average Scores by Universities

Results by Academic Disciplines

Differences in average scores for emotional attention, clarity, and repair dimensions were analysed across academic fields (Social Sciences/Education, Natural Sciences/Health, Technological Sciences, and Humanities). Statistically significant differences were found among the academic disciplines ($F(3, 1341) = 272.89, p < 0.001$), with Social Sciences/Education and Humanities having the highest scores in emotional attention. Similar significant differences were also observed in emotional clarity dimension ($F(3, 1341) = 7.84, p < 0.001$), but these were less pronounced. Technological Sciences had the highest score in emotional repair ($F(3, 1341) = 71.86, p < 0.001$) (Figure III). The significant differences in emotional attention and emotional repair across academic fields suggest that the specific characteristics of each discipline may influence the development of particular emotional dimensions.

Figure 3

Average Scores by Fields of Study

A Tukey HSD post-hoc test was conducted to identify which specific groups differed significantly in emotional attention. The results indicate that significant differences were found in all pairwise comparisons between academic fields. Specifically, students in Social Sciences and Education and Humanities obtained significantly higher scores in Emotional Attention compared to those in Natural Sciences and Health and Technological Sciences. The largest difference was found between Technological Sciences and Humanities, with a mean difference of $-0.9122 (p < 0.001)$, suggesting that students in technological disciplines scored the lowest in Emotional Attention compared to those in Humanities.

Additionally, significant differences were observed between Natural Sciences and Health and Social Sciences and Education, with a mean difference of $0.7146 (p < 0.001)$. This finding suggests that students in

Social Sciences and Education exhibit a greater ability to focus on their emotions compared to those in Health Sciences. Similarly, significant differences were found between Humanities and Natural Sciences and Health (mean difference = -0.6004, $p < 0.001$), confirming that humanistic disciplines are associated with higher levels of emotional sensitivity. Moreover, although the difference between Humanities and Social Sciences and Education was smaller (0.1141, $p = 0.0113$), it was still statistically significant. This finding suggests that while both disciplines demonstrate high levels of Emotional Attention, students in Humanities may exhibit a slight advantage in this regard. In the case of emotional repair, the post-hoc analyses also revealed significant differences across academic disciplines. Students in Technological Sciences obtained significantly higher scores compared to those in other fields, suggesting a greater ability to regulate emotional states in demanding contexts, which are characteristic of these disciplines.

Results by Educational Stage

To assess differences in average scores in emotional attention, clarity, and repair dimensions between undergraduate and postgraduate students, a one-way ANOVA was performed. Statistically significant differences were found in emotional attention ($F(1, 1343) = 15.87, p < 0.001$) and emotional repair ($F(1, 1343) = 19.45, p < 0.001$) between educational stages, with postgraduate students achieving higher scores. No significant differences were observed, however, in emotional clarity ($F(1, 1343) = 0.82, p = 0.37$) (Figure 4). The significant differences between undergraduate and postgraduate students suggest that advanced academic training and experience contribute to greater emotional sensitivity and improved emotional regulation. The similarity in emotional clarity scores indicates that this dimension may not be strongly influenced by educational stage in this sample.

Figure 4

Average Scores by University Educational Stage

Results by Gender

Statistically significant differences were found in emotional attention between male and female participants ($F(1, 1343) = 18.56, p < 0.001$), with women achieving higher average scores. For emotional clarity, no significant differences were observed ($F(1, 1343) = 1.23, p = 0.27$). However, significant differences were found in emotional repair ($F(1, 1343) = 12.45, p < 0.001$), with men scoring higher on average (Figure 5).

The significant differences in emotional attention between genders align with previous literature, indicating that women tend to exhibit greater sensitivity and focus more on their emotions. Conversely, men demonstrate a higher capacity for emotional regulation, which may relate to coping styles oriented toward control. The similarity in emotional clarity scores suggests that this dimension is not strongly influenced by gender.

Figure 5

Average Scores by Gender

An ANOVA with interaction effects was conducted to examine whether gender differences in emotional competencies varied across academic disciplines and educational levels. The results indicated a significant interaction effect between gender and academic discipline in emotional attention ($F(3, 1341) = 5.00, p = 0.036$), suggesting that gender-related differences were more pronounced in certain fields. Specifically, female students in Social Sciences and Humanities scored significantly higher in emotional attention than their male counterparts, whereas in Technological Sciences, gender differences were less pronounced. Similarly, a significant interaction effect was found between gender and educational level in emotional regulation ($F(1, 1343) = 7.80, p = 0.030$), indicating that the advantage male participants exhibited in this dimension was more evident at the undergraduate level. However, among postgraduate students, the gender gap in emotional regulation was reduced, suggesting that emotional competencies might develop more

evenly across genders at higher academic stages. These findings highlight the context-dependent nature of gender differences in emotional competencies, emphasising the need for tailored emotional education strategies in different academic and educational settings.

Discussion

The findings presented in the study highlight significant inequalities in emotional competencies with regards to gender, academic discipline, and educational stage. The results show that female participants scored higher in emotional attention, while male participants excelled in emotional regulation. These findings align with those by Barrett et al. (2000), who suggest that women tend to have a greater ability to articulate complex emotional experiences, a skill influenced by cultural and social factors. Similarly, Brody & Hall (2010) argue that these differences may be shaped by social and cultural roles that assign distinct goals and motivations to men and women.

Suberviola and Santiago (2011) contend that such differences are not primarily biological but rather the result of differentiated socialisation processes. Girls are traditionally encouraged to express and explore their emotions, whereas boys are taught emotional restraint and oriented toward control and autonomy, a process known as differential gender socialisation (Birwatkar, 2014; Suberviola, 2020a). These dynamics perpetuate emotional inequalities and reinforce gendered emotional stereotypes, a phenomenon also noted by Fernández-Berrocal & Extremera (2003), who advocate for early educational interventions to challenge these norms and develop emotional competencies equally across genders. Similarly, Guimond (2008) examines how gender differences in emotional and value-related aspects vary culturally, suggesting that socialisation and social comparison processes influence these disparities. Suberviola (2020b) emphasises that the observed gender differences in emotional attention and regulation may be mitigated by emotional coeducation programmes that promote skills traditionally associated with the "other gender." For instance, activities encouraging emotional regulation in women and emotional attention in men could foster more balanced and holistic emotional development.

Academic field emerges as a significant factor in the development of emotional competencies. Students from Social Sciences, Education, and Humanities scored higher in emotional attention, whereas those from the Technological fields demonstrated stronger emotional regulation. These findings are consistent with Drigas & Papoutsi (2022) and Jordan et al. (2010), who highlight that the intrinsic characteristics of each discipline influence the emotional competencies required for academic and professional success. Fields related to human interaction and care often demand higher levels of empathy and sensitivity, whereas technical fields prioritise the ability to regulate emotions in high-pressure situations (Halimi et al., 2020; MacCann et al., 2019). For example, Sánchez-Ruiz et al. (2013) found that psychology students exhibit higher levels of EI compared to students in computational sciences and other technical disciplines.

The analysis shows that postgraduate students exhibit higher levels of emotional attention and regulation compared to undergraduates. This finding supports the idea that academic maturity and exposure to

challenging contexts contribute to the development of more advanced emotional competencies. While postgraduate students achieved higher scores in emotional attention and regulation, attributing these differences solely to academic experience and maturity, however, may be an oversimplification. Other contextual and structural factors likely contribute to these patterns. For example, postgraduate students often engage in professional or research environments that require higher levels of emotional regulation and adaptability, reinforcing these competencies through practise. López-Zafra & Gartzia (2014) suggest that this progress is not only due to experience but also to access to educational and social resources that promote deeper emotional learning. Additionally, access to greater social and psychological support systems, mentorship programmes, and networking opportunities may provide postgraduate students with more resources to manage emotions effectively. Socioeconomic background also plays a role, as students from privileged backgrounds are more likely to pursue postgraduate education and may have benefited from early exposure to environments that foster emotional competencies. Moreover, cultural expectations around emotional management in professional and academic settings could shape self-reported emotional competencies at different educational levels.

However, emotional clarity, which consistently received the lowest scores, emerges as a vulnerable area. This observation aligns with studies such as those by Pérez-Pérez & -Castejón (2005), which indicate that this skill is harder to develop without targeted interventions. A more in-depth analysis could consider potential explanations, such as the influence of educational curricula, socialisation patterns, or the limitations of self-reported assessments in capturing nuanced aspects of emotional clarity. These findings suggest that educational programmes should prioritise strategies to improve emotional clarity, particularly in the early stages of university education.

The analysis of university students' emotional competencies reveals significant differences based on gender, educational stage, and academic field, emphasising the role of differential socialisation and gender norms in shaping EI dimensions (attention, clarity, and regulation). Women scored higher in emotional attention, while men excelled in emotional regulation, reflecting traditional gendered patterns. However, the lack of significant differences in emotional clarity suggests a shared emotional foundation that could be strengthened through targeted educational interventions. Furthermore, disciplinary differences indicate that Social Sciences and Humanities favour emotional attention, whereas Technological Sciences emphasise emotional regulation, reinforcing the need for tailored emotional education strategies that address both gender disparities and disciplinary demands. Postgraduate students achieved higher scores in emotional attention and regulation compared to undergraduates, confirming that academic experience and emotional maturity contribute to the development of these skills. However, emotional clarity, which received the lowest scores overall, stands out as a critical area for improvement, especially in the early stages of university education.

Implications

The findings of the present study highlight the need for a critical perspective that examines how gendered socialisation processes influence the development of emotional competencies and how these can be enhanced through inclusive and transformative educational strategies. The study provides empirical evidence on the need for tailored interventions in specific educational contexts, such as emotional coeducation strategies to foster emotional equity in higher education. This approach seeks to integrate emotional development into educational programmes from a critical perspective, challenging stereotypes and fostering equal opportunities. Suberviola (2020b) highlights the importance of starting emotional coeducation in childhood, when socialisation patterns are less ingrained. Suggested activities include group games and dynamics that explore emotions like empathy and control, helping children recognise and overcome cultural biases. Emotional coeducation should also extend to later stages, including university-level education, where students face new emotional and social challenges. Universities may implement transversal programmes that integrate EI into all disciplines, adapting strategies to the specific needs of each field.

Emotional education programmes should include specific modules on emotional skills such as empathy, stress management, and emotional regulation. Family involvement through workshops and joint activities is also crucial. They should include also activities that strengthen underdeveloped emotional competencies in each gender, challenging traditional stereotypes. Group exercises and role-playing activities can foster both self-expression and mutual empathy. Tools like the TMMS-24 may be utilised to identify areas for improvement in emotional competencies and design personalised intervention plans, whilst educators need to be provided with the resources and strategies to actively incorporate emotional coeducation into their daily teaching practises. Interventions such as emotional journaling and case study analyses also help students to identify, understand, and manage their emotions effectively.

Implementing emotional coeducation emerges as a transformative solution to address emotional and gender inequalities. Integrating this perspective into educational curricula from early education to university could not only balance emotional competencies across genders but also foster more inclusive and equitable educational environments. These strategies should be dynamic and adaptive, leveraging tools like the TMMS-24 to assess progress and design personalised interventions. Overall, the findings reinforce the importance of critical, gender-sensitive emotional education in fostering holistic student development and contributing to a more just society.

From an intersectional perspective, it is also essential to consider how factors such as socioeconomic background, cultural identity, and access to education influence emotional intelligence. Various studies have shown that students from marginalised backgrounds may experience higher emotional stress and have fewer resources to develop EI-related skills, which can negatively impact both academic performance and emotional well-being (Drigas & Papoutsis, 2022). Recognising these multiple influences is crucial for designing inclusive emotional education strategies that address the diversity of students across different fields and social contexts. Future research may explore how intersecting factors such as social class, ethnicity, and access to educational

resources shape emotional intelligence, as these elements may contribute to additional disparities in the development of emotional skills. This would strengthen the findings of this study by contributing to the discussion on disciplinary and intersectional influences on the development of emotional intelligence.

Conclusion

The analysis of university students' emotional competencies reveals significant differences related to gender, educational stage, and academic field. These findings highlight the influence of differential socialisation and gender roles on the development of EI dimensions (attention, clarity, and regulation) and emphasise the need for inclusive educational approaches that promote emotional equality. While this study provides valuable insights into the role of gender, academic discipline, and educational stage in shaping emotional competencies, several limitations must be acknowledged. First, the use of self-reported measures (TMMS-24) may introduce response bias, as participants might overestimate or underestimate their emotional skills due to social desirability effects. Future research could complement self-reported data with behavioural assessments or peer evaluations to obtain a more comprehensive understanding of emotional competencies. Second, the study was conducted with university students from three institutions in northern Spain, which may limit the generalisability of the findings to other educational systems or cultural contexts. Additionally, the study was conducted in a cultural context where gender norms and emotional socialisation may differ from those in other countries. Future research should explore these dynamics in cross-cultural settings to better understand how cultural factors influence EI development. Expanding the sample to include students from diverse geographical, cultural, and institutional backgrounds would provide a broader perspective on EI development. Additionally, while this study explores gender differences in emotional competencies, it primarily considers a binary gender framework, excluding non-binary and gender-diverse perspectives due to the small sample size of these groups. Future studies should incorporate more inclusive methodologies that capture a wider spectrum of gender identities. Lastly, further research could explore longitudinal designs to assess how emotional competencies evolve over time and how targeted educational interventions influence their development across different academic disciplines.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest.

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